

README- Raw Data Upload for the Article

“Phenothiazine redox mediators boost photocatalytic hydrogen evolution”

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Raw Data for the various analytical methods is compressed into one .zip file each.

Compound names:

PTH = Phenothiazine (sometimes abbr. as PTZ)

MPT = Me-PTZ

PEG-PT = PEG-PTZ

TolPT-PEG = MG22b

TolPT-diPEG = MG22

P1 = MG26

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)

- Raw Data for each compound or as MNOVA Data (readable with MESTRELAB MestReNova)

Mass Spectroscopy (MS)

- raw data file for each compound

Ultraviolet and Visible Light Spectroscopy (UV/Vis)

- .txt files

Electrochemical measurements in Solution

- .txt files for the measurement and for the reference vs. Fc/Fc+

Hydrogen evolution measurements:

- .txt files; or .run files (readable with MSWS 8)